

6GSNS

Funded by
the European Union

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

Deliverable D6.1

Date: 30/3/2023

Version: 1.0

Grant Agreement	101096328
Document number	D6.1
Document title	Initial Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
Lead Beneficiary	EURE
Editor(s)	Halid Hrasnica (EURE)
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Dissemination level	Public
Contractual date of delivery	31 March 2023
Status	Final
Version	1.0
File name	6G-SANDBOX_D6.1_V1.0.pdf

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ABSTRACT

This document presents the initial dissemination and exploitation plan of the 6G-SANDBOX project. The document also provides information on the completed project branding / project logo as well as other components of the graphical project identity. 6G-SANDBOX launched its website and further social media channels, as presented in the document as well. Finally, an initial plan for implementation of the open calls is presented.

KEYWORDS

Impact, Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Standardization, SNS participation, Project Branding, Website and Social Media, Open Calls, Planning

1 INTRODUCTION

To achieve its impact creation objectives, the 6G-SANDBOX project consortium established an overall dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy as well as the corresponding initial plans, which are presented in the document. The strategy includes further details on the identified targeted groups, for the dissemination and exploitation activities, as well as the first set of planned interactions with the groups, the initial planning for publications in journals and conferences, planning for participation at various events and organization of the project workshops, overall exploitation activity plans, contributions to standards, and the project commitments on the SNS program level.

The document provides information on the project branding, which includes a clear definition of the project logo as well as other components of the graphical project identity. The 6G-SANDBOX website has been published, including establishment of social media channels.

Finally, the deliverable presents an initial plan for implementation of the 6G-SANDBOX open calls, including topics planned for the 1st OC.

Note, that this deliverable is a living document, reporting on the updated plan and established 6G SANDBOX dissemination environment, and will be continuously updated and reviewed during the project lifetime.

2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

To assist the reader of this deliverable, a Dissemination and Communication definition is presented briefly in accordance with the European Commission's guidelines for projects under the Horizon Europe umbrella¹.

Communication: 'Communication' refers to the measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The communication activities must be planned and implemented from the outset (and continue throughout the entire action), with a comprehensive communication plan that defines clear objectives (adapted to various relevant target audiences) and identifies a solid plan for the communication activities including a description and timing for each activity. In every Horizon Europe project proposal, a communication plan should be included to ensure that project results are widely communicated to the public, even outside the R&I community

Dissemination: 'Dissemination' refers to the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium. In every Horizon Europe work plan, a dissemination plan should be included to ensure the sharing of the knowledge produced.

2.1 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES OVERVIEW

In the following sections a comprehensive set of dissemination, communication and community building activities will be presented and are expected to contribute to the overall success of 6G-SANDBOX. The main goal of the 6G-SANBOX dissemination and communication plan is to build project awareness and spread its results to the broadest possible audience and to attract potential users.

To accomplish this goal, 6G-SANDBOX will divide communication into the following two major paths:

1. General communication activities, which will be focused on primarily in the first months of the project and will target a broad public audience,
2. A set of more dedicated dissemination activities, which will present 6G-SANDBOX advances and outcomes to scientific communities, academia, targeted SME's, relevant industries, and end-users. As the project progresses, this type of communication will become more important, and concrete results will become the focus of the dissemination strategy.

Within this context, throughout the lifetime of the project, two specific types of actions will structure the 6G-SANDBOX dissemination and communication strategy:

1. **Online actions:** Based on the use of social media, website and other online resources (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn, digital resources).
2. **Offline actions:** Based on on-site and face-to-face actions (e.g., events, workshops, presentations, trials).

To build and implement an effective 6G-SANDBOX dissemination and communication plan, it is necessary to continuously analyse and update the project's progress and its environment, through the institution of a process that will run throughout the project lifetime, within the following framework of actions:

- Determine the various types of target audiences.
- Define the dissemination and communication plan's purpose and objectives.
- Establish communication and dissemination channels.
- Develop and update, if needed, the Communication and Dissemination Action Plan.

¹ <https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-04/HE%20Glossary%20Bridge2HE.pdf>

- Quantify the results and set KPI's (e.g., number of papers, visits on website, etc.) and provide feedback to dissemination and communication planning.
- Involve partners in dissemination so they can use their established communication channels to spread and amplify the message.
- Define and establish monitoring, tracking, evaluation and statistical mechanisms.

2.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

6G-SANDBOX will heavily communicate and disseminate its activities, advancements and key outputs to a specific target audience. 6G-SANDBOX project will engage in dissemination, communication and community building toward industry and services, including MNO, vendors of network (mainly SMEs), standardization bodies, regulators, 6G researchers, as well as citizens and vertical sectors which will benefit from 6G as illustrated in Figure 1.

The main **target groups** that would benefit from 6G-SANDBOX include the following:

- **Vendors of network and service components**, including the entire chain, from device makers, radio equipment, transport (fixed and NTN), core, computing and storage, to app and service developers. They will access the existing sites to validate new technologies in an early state before being offered to the market. The ability to connect to other functionalities and tests in end-to-end conditions will be key. This group is mainly composed by SMEs.
- **MNOs, operators of private networks and providers of 6G services to verticals**, assuming that the exploitation of 6G will involve more actors. They will make validation in a project sandbox to compare solutions, to check interoperability and for showcasing before adoption in production.
- **Participants in the JU SNS programme**, considering both third parties involved in the open calls and participants in next phases of the JU SNS. They will use the project results to validate their Proof of Concepts or more mature technologies in a trusted environment under reasonable accession conditions.
- **EU researchers in 6G**, supported or not by other national and international initiatives beyond JU SNS and mainly in research institutions that cannot afford the cost of creating specific testbeds for their experiments. They will have access to large-scale setups fully equipped with state-of-the-art validation tools to evaluate their proposals.
- **SDOs, Regulators, public authorities or vertical associations** that define public policies or recommendation to specific sectors. They will approach the project sites to get support for specific evaluations and consultation from the project sites to elaborate analysis for decision making regarding spectrum, technologies, services, needs for future regulations, etc.
- **Society in general**, including vertical sectors and citizens that use 6G for personal applications and companies not directly involved in 6G but offering services based on "Internet of Sense" (media and entertainment, Health, PPDR services, education, etc). They will benefit from the 6G technologies and services promoted by the other target groups.

Figure 1: 6G-SANDBOX TARGET AUDIENCE

2.3 PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

Communication and dissemination activities are critical for the project's knowledge diffusion, raising awareness, and attracting potential supporters, industries and verticals, end users, and customers. The primary goals of the 6G-SANDBOX dissemination and communication actions are as follows:

- To raise awareness of the project to relevant industries and stakeholders.
- To communicate and disseminate project activities, innovations, findings and recommendations.
- To build communication connection and enhance collaboration with other initiatives from the SNS-JU program, ensuring alignment with ongoing projects and collaboration.
- To attain high project visibility and increased awareness to the broadest audience.

2.4 PROJECT BRANDING POLICY

Since public perception of the project is critical, all communication elements should be consistent and relevant. The most important criterion is consistency because it is necessary to preserve the integrity of the overall aesthetic. Moreover, the purpose of graphic design must be relevant to the overall goals of the project must communicate them efficiently and clearly.

This section gives an overview and brief description of how to apply 6G-SANDBOX branded identity and design elements to various materials.

2.4.1 LOGO DESCRIPTION

The 6G-SANDBOX logo (Figure 2) was developed at the beginning of the project aiming to provide a clear identity and appearance. The logos variations can be found in **Error! Reference source not found..**

The logo has been designed and developed with the following criteria in mind:

1. The logo provides 6G-SANDBOX with an icon that reflects its mission and values.
2. The logo consists of the following two defining elements:
 - o **Graphical element:** Contains a 3D box which is built by a number “6” on the left and a letter “G” on the right, which are slightly angled and connected to one another. The curved lines, which are on the side of this graphic and cascade outward, represent Connectivity.
 - o **Textual element:** Contains the title of the project.

3. The main colours of the logo include a shade of grey and a shade of beige/gold. Grey was selected as a neutral and timeless colour and is typically used as background for more vibrant colours. The shade of beige/gold was selected to make connotation with the logo's first synonym 'SAND'. A clear and modern font - **COMFORTAA / Bold (Google Fonts)** has been used for the textual element.
4. The project logo is available on Projects Repository - SharePoint - for all partners free to use.

Figure 2: 6G-SANDBOX logo

2.4.2 GENERAL TEMPLATES

In pursuance of a consistent brand identity, all templates have the typical 6G-SANDBOX look. The templates are developed for internal and external use. The general guidelines followed regarding these templates are summarised below:

Colour Palette

1. **Beige/Gold Color: RGB 205 159 43, HEX: #CD9F2B, CMYK: 18.5,35,95,7**
2. **Grey Color: RGB 56 56 56, HEX: #383838 CMYC: 67.5, 58, 55, 62.5**
3. **White Color**
4. **Black Color**

These templates have been shared with all partners and are available on Projects repository (SharePoint) and are accessible to all partners.

2.4.3 PRESENTATION TEMPLATES

The PowerPoint template shown below in Figure 3, has been created for internal and external presentations such as conferences, speeches, meetings and in general presenting research results.

Figure 3: 6G-SANDBOX PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

2.4.4 DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

A general template has been created for all deliverables, which gives a detailed description of how it must be used. From Abstract to conclusion, the template provides a brief definition and explains formatting of headings, tables, figures, etc. The selected font is Calibri.

Furthermore, predefined settings have been included in headers and footers. These help to ensure that all partners can quickly and easily create a well-structured document for their deliverables (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: 6G-SANDBOX DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

2.4.5 ADDITIONAL OBLIGATORY ELEMENTS

The various communication materials (brochures, posters, newsletters, etc.) which are or will be created must also carry the following obligatory elements.

1. **European flag** and the following statements:

'6G-SANDBOX has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101096328'

And as a secondary disclaimer: ***Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission (granting authority). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.***

2. 6GSNS logo:

3. Project's details:

Topic: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-STREAM-C-01-01

Type of Action: HORIZON-JU-RIA

Duration: 36 months

Start Date: 01/01/2023

4. **Social Media** logos with links (when digital) to the corresponding platforms

5. **Project's Website:** <https://6g-sandbox.eu/>

The creatives and the corresponding templates are digitally available on Projects repository (SharePoint). Every partner will be able to download and print the communication tools and use the layout for specific communication activities, such as press conferences, internal communication, and others.

2.5 CHANNELS OF COMMUNICATIONS

In this sub-section, the Channels of Communication are presented briefly, justifying the selection. The Communication Action Plan is described in sub-section 2.7.

2.5.1 WEBSITE

The website will be the major tool for communication and promotion of the project. The design of the website (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/>) reflects the overall visual identity of the project and transmits the knowledge. The public project website enables external and internal audiences to be informed on the project's approach and objectives, its news and events and provides the contact information of the project leader.

Website Characteristics:

1. Domain name purchased for 7 years by University of Malaga
2. Hosting offered by INFOLYSIS
3. Designed and developed by INFOLYSIS & NCSR teams
4. Maintained and updated with latest content, activities and news by INFOLYSIS
5. Live since mid-January 2023
6. Developed in WordPress
7. Google Analytics enabled
8. Contact Form provided (addressing Project Coordinator, Technical manager and T6.2 leader)

Website Navigation Pane

The website is organized into seven menu sections across the top banner: Home, Pilot 6G Sites, Objectives, Consortium, Dissemination, News, Contact, which are displayed in the Navigation Pane. Accordingly, the logo of the project is placed on the left side and the social media links on the right side. See Figure 5.

ABOUT

Figure 5: WEBSITE NAVIGATION PANE

Website Footer

The website footer contains the project details along with the Grant Agreement text and the Site Map menu. Also, the Tags which have been used in the News Section are set in the footer. Finally, the 6G-SNS IA and European Commission logos are visible here as instructed. See Figure 6.

Figure 6: WEBSITE FOOTER

2.5.1.1 WEBSITE STRUCTURE IN DETAIL

In this sub-section, the Menus and sub-Menus are presented in detail.

2.5.1.1.1 HOME

The logo as well as the core essence of the project are both displayed in the Home Page (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/>). As the visitor scrolls down the page, the project Overview is presented as well as four photos with direct links to the each of the 6G Pilot Sites (Athens, Berlin, Malaga, and Oulu). Below the Pilots there are links

to the 6G Pilots Sites Menu and the Contact Form Menu in order to facilitate the user. At the bottom of the Home Page a carousel provides the logos of the Partners as well as a link to the Consortium Menu, where the visitor can find more details about the partners. See Figure 7.

Figure 7: HOME PAGE

2.5.1.1.2 PILOT 6G SITES MENU

The Pilot 6G Site menu (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/>) references the current components that comprise the platforms around Europe and presents the new integrated features. Also, the visitor can find information about the three main sectors that will be under the scope of the Consortium. See Figure 8.

The Pilot 6G Menu contains the following four sub-menus, which present details about each European platform:

- Athens (see Figure 9) (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/athens/>)
- Berlin (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/berlin/>)
- Malaga (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/malaga/>)
- Oulu (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/pilot-6g-sites/oulu/>)

Figure 8: PILOT 6G PAGE

Figure 9: ATHENS PLATFORM PAGE

2.5.1.1.3 OBJECTIVES MENU

The Objectives page (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/objectives/>), introduces the 6G-SANDBOX Platform, the main Objectives of 6G-SANDBOX and the metrics to evaluate the fulfilment of these goals.

OBJECTIVES

MOTIVATION AND SCOPE

At the dawn of the new era in telecommunications after the successful deployment of 5G networks, the principles of 6G networks and services are being designed, while disruptive visions regarding the 6G contribution in socioeconomic impact (well-defined as *SDG by UN*) are being composed. Indeed, the first signs for shaping the expectations from 6G have emerged, where a convergence of digital, physical, and human domains is envisioned. In this revolutionary path, the contribution from technology and research experimentation facilities of emerging 6G technologies is expected to be crucial. Those facilities will function as one-stop shops which will help companies dynamically respond to the 6G digital challenges and expectations. This potential of experimentation facilities has been validated already through the 5G paradigm, where 5G pan-European facilities, such as 5GENESIS, 5G-VINNI, or 5G-EVE, supported the 5G digital transformation and the trial of innovative applications and services. However, the need of experimentation facilities is further amplified in the beyond 5G era, as depicted in multiple Standards Organisation (SDOs) and research-oriented references, due to the disruptive expectations that 6G brings, creating a direct need for trials and experimentation towards the creation of novelty. For instance, in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA 2021-27), the need for experimentation is defined as one of the key recommended actions towards 6G, while ITU has recently established a Focus Group on Testbeds Federations for IMT-2020 and beyond. In the same context, the key objectives of SNS R&I Work Programme 2021-2022, regarding Stream C calls, are formulated around the development of experimental infrastructures, that will validate 6G technologies and use cases. As a response to this challenge, the 6G-SANDBOX project is dedicated to providing clear and tangible contributions towards an experimentation ecosystem for 6G in Europe.

Figure 10: 6G-SANDBOX Objectives Page

2.5.1.1.4 CONSORTIUM MENU

The Consortium Menu page (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/consortium/>) includes a listing of the 18 Partners which form the Consortium. Each row in the table contains a direct link to each partner’s website.

CONSORTIUM

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	Keysight Technologies Belgium BV	KEYB	Belgium
2	Universidad de Malaga	UMA	Spain
3	Keysight Technologies Denmark APS	KEYD	Denmark
4	Fogus Innovations & Services P.C.	FOG	Greece
5	INFOLYSIS P.C.	INF	Greece
6	Boreal Technology & Investments SL	OWO	Spain
7	Telefonica Investigacion Y Desarrollo SA	TEL	Spain

Figure 11: Consortium Page

2.5.1.1.5 DISSEMINATION MENU

The Dissemination page (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/>) has seven sub-menus shown with icons corresponding to the sub-menu content (Publications, Press Releases, Deliverables, Newsletters, Workshops, Articles, Events). There is also one additional icon, named Media-Videos, which links to 6G-SANDBOX YouTube Channel. From this same page, visitor can also download the Communication Material of the project, poster and brochure in PDF format. See Figure 12.

Figure 12: Dissemination Page and Sub-Menus

Dissemination Page Sub-Menus

Each of the seven sub-menus is described in more detail below.

1. **Publications:** In this page, all the 6G-SANDBOX Publications (conference papers, white papers, etc.) will be uploaded with links to the corresponding document. (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/publications/>)
2. **Workshops, Presentations and Trials** (see Figure 1313(06)): This page displays in three different tables the different types of Consortium activities, presented by Name of the event, the Partner who contributed, Date and Location and Title of the presentations. The Title cells in the tables also have a link to the actual PDF file.

6G-SANDBOX organizes/co-organizes several workshops, participates in conferences and delivers presentations in various events, performs trials and test as per the defined use cases. All these related communication and dissemination activities are summarized below.

Presentations

EVENT	Partner	DATE / LOCATION	TITLE
ETSI Research Conference 2023	Lenovo	6th -7th February 2023	"The 6G-SANDBOX approach towards 6G experimentation" PDF
SNS Luncetime Webinar	UMA	15th February 2023	6G-SANDBOX Overview PDF

Figure 13: Workshops, Presentations and Trials Page

1. **Articles:** This page (see Figure 14) lists every article, with Title and link, which has been written and published on various websites and contribute to the 6G-SANDBOX buzz. (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/articles/>)

ARTICLES

6G-SANDBOX articles are published in several media such as journals, newspapers, websites, newsletters etc. All published articles will be presented in detail on the following sections.

1. Pan-European testbed project takes step into 6G era

<https://electronics360.globalspec.com/article/19221/pan-european-testbed-project-takes-step-into-6g-era>

2. Keysight Technologies to coordinate pan-European 6G testbed

<https://www.capacitymedia.com/article/2b3x4lr94pcy245ebjdvk/news/keysight-technologies-to-coordinate-pan-european-6g-testbed>

3. Keysight Technologies co-ordinates pan-European 6G testbed

Figure 14: Articles Page

1. **Press Releases:** This page includes the Press Releases which were diffused by Partners in their company's websites. (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/press-releases/>)

Figure 15: Press Releases Page

- 2. Deliverables:** On this page the visitor will be able to find the titles and the days of submission of all public and confidential Deliverables. The public Deliverables will be available for viewing through a PDF link.
(<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/deliverables/>)
- 3. Newsletters:** All Newsletters which will be issued quarterly will be available for the visitor on this page. The table consists of three columns; Issue, Period covered and Download.
(<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/newsletter/>)
- 4. Events:** On this page, (see Figure 16), all past and upcoming Events in which the Consortium will participate or have already participated, will be reported.

(<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/events/>)

(<https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/events/>)

Figure 16: Events Page

2.5.1.1.6 NEWS MENU

The News menu (see Figure 17) is divided in two sub-menus. The News Page is where all the activities of the Consortium are reported, but also the general news which are related to the project (e.g., 5G-PPP or 6G SNS or related Working Groups News). The Events Page is where the visitor can read about various activities of the Consortium with photos and details about the event (e.g., Presentation in ETSI Research Conference). (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/category/news/>)

A White Paper from Architecture WG is released.

February 21, 2023 / In News / by Anastasios Gogos

This white paper summarizes the main findings from the European research landscape on the vision of the 6G architecture. Such a design vision is derived from around 45 projects starting from October 2020 in all relevant areas of 5G while paving the way towards 6G, within the 5G Public Private-Partnership (5G PPP) in the scope of the European Framework for Research and Innovation. <https://zenodo.org/record/7313232#.Y-TCQnZBxD8>

Dr. Salkintzis from Lenovo presents 6G-SANDBOX in ETSI Research Conference

February 14, 2023 / In Events, News / by Anastasios Gogos

On the 6th-7th of February, ETSI Research Conference took place in Sophia Antipolis, France. In this context Dr. Apostolis Salkintzis, from Lenovo provided a high-level overview of the 6G-SANDBOX project and explained how it can help us in our journey to 6G.

The main objective of this project is to build an experimentation platform that can help us evaluate new technologies towards 6G and measure important 6G KPIs and KVs.

It was also pointed out that the 6G-SANDBOX project is open to third-parties willing to contribute either with new technologies, or with new use-cases and experiments. The most important question from the audience was whether the 6G-SANDBOX platform will be able to interoperate with other experimentation platforms towards creating federated experimentation platforms. For more information visit: <https://www.etsi.org/events/2130-etsi-research-conference>

CATEGORIES

- Events
- News

Figure 17: News Page

2.5.1.1.7 CONTACT MENU

This page contains a Contact Form through which the person who is interested to contact with the project can do so. Next to the contact form there is a map, which lists the country origins for each member of the consortium.

(<https://6g-sandbox.eu/contact/>)

Figure 18: Contact Form Page

2.5.1.1.8 OPEN CALLS MENU

This menu (see Figure 18) delivers relevant information about the two Open Calls for those who would like to participate. The main page gives basic information about 6G-SANDBOX with a sub-menu named Open Call #1, which communicates the more detailed information about the first Open Call. (<https://6g-sandbox.eu/opencall/>)

Figure 19: Open Calls Page

2.5.2 SOCIAL MEDIA

In addition to the project website, social media platforms are available to assist to effectively communicate 6G-SANDBOX activities, accomplishments, and highlights, as well as raise project's overall awareness. The project's presence on a variety of social media channels resulted in greater exposure of the project's impact to diverse audiences in a cost-effective and efficient manner.

To improve communication of the project's impact and results and enhance communication and reach different target audiences, the 6G-SANDBOX is present since M1 on the most popular channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube) and are listed below with links.

- a. **LinkedIn:** 6G-SANDBOX Project (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/6g-sandbox-project/>)

LinkedIn is the largest and most powerful professional and business networking website that will allow the Consortium to effectively communicate the achievements and impact of 6G-SANDBOX to the relevant industries.

Figure 20: LinkedIn Page

b. **Twitter:** @6gsandbox (<https://twitter.com/6gsandbox>)

Twitter is one of the most popular social media platforms and it can be used to promote 6G-SANDBOX's content to the general public to broaden its global reach and effect.

Figure 21: Twitter Page

- c. **Instagram:** 6gsandbox (<https://www.instagram.com/6gsandbox/>)

Instagram is one of the most popular platforms to share images and videos. 6G-SANDBOX will take advantage of this network by posting images featuring the project work and achievements to reach the wider audience.

Figure 22: Instagram Page

d. **Facebook:** 6G-SANDBOX (<https://www.facebook.com/6gsandbox>)

Facebook is one of the most recognized social media platforms and 6G-SANDBOX is present there. The effect and the high popularity of this platform completes the project’s social media presence and together with Instagram targets the general audience and society in general.

Figure 23: Facebook Page

e. **YouTube:** 6G-SANDBOX Project (<https://www.youtube.com/@6gsandboxproject>)

YouTube is the most significant video distribution platform on the Internet. The creation of video content which carries the 6G-SANDBOX's key concept is more detail, will assist to reach and attract project's audience more effectively.

Figure 24: YouTube Page

2.5.3 NEWSLETTERS

The Newsletter is an essential element of the communication plan as it serves to disseminate the latest news and achievements at regular intervals. The aim is to keep the community informed and engaged with the project, as well as to increase its credibility and exposure.

2.5.4 PRINTED MATERIAL

Brochures, posters and other printed material are supportive, but valuable tools, for the communication of the project and will be used to communicate the key elements of 6G-SANDBOX project, including the project's name, logo, objectives, results, etc., and consequently to raise awareness and increase engagement during dissemination and communication events.

2.5.5 PRESS RELEASES

Press Releases are an important means of communication to spread the word and help reach the broader audience through the Press, to drive traffic to the website and to build the project's credibility. Press Releases usually are released by each individual partner especially in the beginning of the project or when a major achievement has been completed.

2.5.6 VIDEOS

Videos are a means of communication which create strong engagement by attracting the attention of the viewer by providing richer content and by efficiently conveying the key messages.

2.6 MEANS OF DISSEMINATION

In this sub-section, the Means of Dissemination are presented briefly, justifying the selection. The actual Communication Action Plan is described in sub-section 2.7.

2.6.1 PUBLICATIONS IN JOURNALS

One of the most fundamental paths for disseminating scientific findings is publication in peer-reviewed journals with a high impact factor. Publishing in the appropriate technical journals will increase the visibility of the 6G-SANDBOX project among other 6G SNS projects. In addition, technical journals make the work more discoverable within the scientific and academic community and accessible in specialised distribution networks such as libraries, organizations, and institutes. Both technical and academia partners are expected to demonstrate scientific excellence not only by an outstanding number of papers in journals but also with publications in prestigious international conferences (with acknowledgment to the 6G-SANDBOX), and workshops

2.6.2 PRESENTATIONS AND EXHIBITIONS IN SCIENTIFIC EVENTS AND FORA

Presentations at scientific and relevant industry events and fora are a great opportunity for gaining valuable feedback from the targeted research, industry and business community while increasing the credibility of the project. Also, being present with a booth increases even more the visibility and the gives the opportunity to showcase project's achievements by demonstrating project's results.

2.6.3 ORGANIZATION AND CO-ORGANISATION OF EVENTS (WORKSHOPS/SPECIAL SESSIONS/WEBINARS)

Educational events such as workshops, special sessions and webinars, are crucial in order to attract and guide all relevant stakeholders and end-users through the technologies and the results of the project and provide information on all aspects relating to 6G-SANDBOX. Independent experts both from industry and academia will also be invited.

2.6.4 ACTIVE PARTICIPATION AT SNS JU PROGRAM

6G-SANDBOX partners are aware of the contractual commitment of the SNS JU and they acknowledge the roles and commitments of the European Commission, the 6G-IA, and commits to constructive interactions with these bodies. The technical manager and deputy technical manager will participate in the JU SNS program level meetings and Working Groups devoted to technical aspects. The reader can read more in Collaboration at SNS program level

2.7 COMMUNICATION PLAN AND DISSEMINATION ACTION PLAN

2.7.1 INTRODUCTION

In this section, the Communication and Dissemination Action Plan is presented in more detail focusing on each medium/tool and providing the major guidelines (timeline, KPI's, etc.) for the successful and effective communication of the project. The Action plan will primarily consider the wide public audience via means of communication, and will involve also a set of more targeted actions, i.e., the dissemination activities, dedicated to the presentation of 6G-SANDBOX technical advances and outcomes to the scientific communities, academia, end-users and corresponding industries.

2.7.2 ENVISIONED ACTIVITIES AND PLAN

6G-SANDBOX is engaged in a comprehensive and well-structured set of activities to ensure an extensive promotion and effective demonstration of the developed concepts, technologies and will heavily promote its key outputs to already defined target audience, with the objective to spread its seeds across the scientific community and beyond. One of the objectives is to have the 6G being adopted and deployed in more facilities. This work will then be used as widely as possible and have its work progressed to ensure sustainability beyond the completion of the project. All the activities will be supported by the Consortium members in order to implement high-impact dissemination actions.

This plan includes both offline and online communications, participation to and organisation of events, contributions to standardisation, interaction with other SNS JU projects, WGs and liaisons with relevant national / local initiatives wherever is possible and global relevant organisations. While the planned activities and their timing will be enhanced in the first months of the project, the core structure of the envisioned 6G-SANDBOX communication and dissemination plan has been organised in the following Stages and with the following means per Audience level demonstrated in Table 1 and

Table 2 .

Table 1: 6G-SANDBOX Communication and Dissemination Plan Core Structure

Table 1: 6G-SANDBOX Communication and Dissemination Plan Core Structure	
Phase A M1-M6	O1: To create awareness of the project among the full range of general public and media. O2: To provide a clear view of the project's concept, goals and expected results.
Phase B M7-M18	O3: To create an active community of general public audience/followers and collect feedback to be considered by the project's activities. O4: To raise awareness and visibility of the project's results.
Phase C M19-M36	O5: To prepare the ground for the exploitation of project's results by creating market demand for provided innovation. O6: To ensure sufficient communication of exploitation results even after the end of the project.

Table 2: 6G-SANDBOX Communication and Dissemination Means per Audience Level

Table 2: 6G-SANDBOX communication audience levels	
Audience Levels	Communication Means and Tools
Project Level	Branding/Logo, Email project list, Report templates, Presentation templates, Project Coordination Manuals, Project Workshops
National Level	Branding/Logo, Brochures/Leaflets, Press releases, Articles and Newsletters, Demos/Showcases in local events, Local Workshops and Info Days.
International Level	Branding/Logo, Social Media Channels (Twitter/LinkedIn/Facebook/Instagram/YouTube), Printed material, Stickers, Posters, Project Website, Press releases, Magazine articles, Trials, General Public Conferences, trainings/business info days.

2.7.3 COMMUNICATION PLAN

6G-SANDBOX will deliver a comprehensive communications programme aimed at promoting the project and its results and successes. This will include communication to the media and the general public, in a structured and effective manner, also engaging them in an interactive way. The communication plan and associated activities (e.g., development of the project's identity, brand, website, and social channels) will be developed in detail under task T6.1 in WP6. The Communication plan will incorporate the specific objectives and key messages addressed to relevant target communication audience groups, setting out clear descriptions and timings for each activity. The aim will be to ensure the visibility of the project and its key outcomes, to ensure they can be understood also by a non-technical audience. The integrated approach to communication combines a mix of traditional and disruptive communications channels. Communications activities targeting large numbers of stakeholders will use "push" communication channels with broad reach (e.g., social media, website, newsletters) while activities targeting smaller group of stakeholders (e.g., policy-makers, funding organisations) will use targeted "pull/interactive" channels such as workshops, presentations, targeted electronic communications, etc. As already defined, the target audience for communication will be SMEs and large industries in a wide range of Vertical Stakeholders, Technology Providers and Entrepreneurs, Press and General Public, Service Consumers, EU technology platforms users, etc.

In specific, 6G-SANDBOX's communication strategy targets a two-way exchange through social media channels and other communication means (in contrast to the dissemination activities, which focus mainly on one-way feed of the project achievements, primarily at the scientific level). All actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the project's own community, including the media and the public and reaching out

the society, are considered Communication activities. The main objective of those is to promote the project itself and its results so as to be understood by the non-specialist (e.g., the media and the public).

In the following sub-sections, we specialize the communication action plan per communication channel.

2.7.3.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

The Project website was developed in M1 and went online in the middle of January 2023. As already stated, it contains all relevant project information such as the objectives, Dissemination activities, deliverables, brochures and posters, as well as the 6G-SANDBOX Consortium and partner details. The content of the website is supported by all project partners to provide a common view of the project and will be updated regularly, at least once per week, providing a good overview of the major project activities and related industry news. Finally, a Google Analytics account has already been associated with the project website to provide useful insight on how to improve its impact. This is a continuous communication activity from M1 to M36 plus four years after project ends.

In terms of traffic, the expected KPI is to attract annually more than 5,000 visitors.

2.7.3.2 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

6G-SANDBOX will adopt social networks for dissemination and communication purposes. The different social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram) will be used to complement 6G-SANDBOX's website. Through these networks, 6G-SANDBOX will advertise its results, informing and reaching out the society and general public for the benefits of the project research, announce events, communicate the recent results and provide a platform for discussion. 6G-SANDBOX hosts a dedicated YouTube channel that will periodically include related recordings/videos. This is a continuous activity from M1 to M36.

As relevant content plays a crucial role in achieving communication objectives, the content will be elaborated in such a way, to meet the different platform's and target audience's profile.

LinkedIn/Twitter: General content but later more technical and project-focused posts targeting at technical and scientific audience.

Facebook/Instagram: General content to technical and the non-technical audience includes posts on 6G-SANDBOX topics of general interest and communication of all dissemination and showcasing activities.

YouTube: Addressing the general audience (technical and non-technical) with videos focused on presentations, conferences, events, tutorials, etc.

More specifically, the social media posts will cover the following activities using a variety of media content, such as photos, videos and URL links:

- News and updates on the 6G-SANDBOX activities and progression of project's tasks and deliverables.
- Papers and presentations originating from workshops, conferences, journals etc.
- Project showcases/demonstrations.
- Publications in articles, online sources, newspapers.
- Upcoming events, Open Calls prompting stakeholders for participation, papers (and Call for Papers), etc.
- Newsletter issues.
- Articles on related industry related and 6G topics.

In addition, all the social media channels can be found in the footer of the project's official website, of the Newsletters and of all the rest of communication channels with activated links leading to the corresponding platform.

To keep updated, our target audiences currently receive an average rate of two posts per week. The hashtags **#learnabout6Gsandbox**, **#6gsandbox**, **#innovation**, **#newproject** and **#research**, are used to give the core essence of the project and the hashtags **#6G** and **#SNS** and **#SNSJU** (in LinkedIn and Twitter a tag **@SNSJU** replaces the hashtag as more appropriate) are used in order to reference the SNS JU and engage the 6G community with 6G-SANDBOX project as illustrated in Figure 25:. Also, the hashtags **#Europeanproject**, **#horizoneurope** and **#eu** are regularly selected in order to demonstrate the relation with the EU. Finally, hashtags or tags are used with the names of the companies/institutions who form the Consortium or/and tags to the name of the representatives, wherever is possible. Sometimes, and depending on the length of the text in Twitter, not all the hashtags are available due to the characters limitation of the platform.

In terms of followers, the expected KPI is to attract more than 1,000 followers as a total across all platforms.

Figure 25: Instagram Post Hashtag Example

2.7.3.3 PRINTED MATERIAL (BROCHURE, POSTER ETC)

The Consortium will prepare printed promotional material such as brochures, posters, stationary material and stickers. Printed material will be provided to the events by the participants (e.g., workshops, conferences, etc.), where the project will have a booth and/or demo. Even though this communication activity was officially scheduled to start in M4 and continue until M36, the needs of the project started earlier so the first poster and brochure area already designed and used. The Poster (Figure 26) was designed in A1 dimensions and the brochure is a tri-fold document (Figure 27:), and they can both be downloaded in PDF format here <https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/>.

Modularity
Openness
Reusability
Innovation
Sustainability

Testbeds for the emerging European 6G ecosystem

Revolutionary proposals to move from 5G to 6G need end-to-end experimental infrastructure to evaluate and validate early Proof of Concepts in a large scale environment. Across Europe, there is a need for shared, accessible, cost-effective experimental infrastructure. 6G-SANDBOX, a Smart Network and Services (SNS) project, provides modular, secure, and digital twin-enabled facilities in 4 platforms across Europe. The 6G-SANDBOX promises continuous upgrade and expansion to support innovative 6G technologies and use cases.

6G-SANDBOX OBJECTIVES

1. Central test facilities in Europe to support the long term evolutions 6G infrastructure.
2. A modular 6G infrastructure distributed in four EU sites (Berlin | Malaga | Athens | Oulu).
3. An open management platform to provide zero touch management.
4. Automated experimentation framework to evaluate 6G Key Performance Indicators and Key Value Indicators.
5. Create an ecosystem under the SNS JU umbrella that will allow the adoption of components from Stream B projects and enable the hosting of 6G use cases, through open calls, during the project lifetime and through the offering from Stream D projects.

Layered Architecture:

1. Physical Infrastructure Layer providing end-to-end 6G-enabled connectivity.
2. Resource Management Layer manages computational and network resources and forming them as Trial Networks for experimentation.
3. Experimentation lifecycle Layer to provision and control the experimentation process.

Pan-European Distribution of experimentation platforms
(Athens | Berlin | Malaga | Oulu)

6G-SANDBOX will fund open calls inviting the broad European community of developers and researchers to experiment by using the 6GSANDBOX Trial Networks in Malaga, Athens, Berlin & Oulu.

OC-1: Open Call for submissions Spring 2023
OC-2: Open Call for submissions Summer 2024
 Total 1.79M€ funding provided

6G-SANDBOX Ambitions

- Experimentation Processes & Facilities
- Disruptive wireless
- Fixed/RAN/NTN integration
- Deterministic networking enablers
- Interaction with Network Core
- AI/ML network evolution
- Security as a Service
- Edge-cloud continuum
- Digital twins
- XR-Haptics

<https://6g-sandbox.eu/>

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 SMART DATE: 08/03/2023

Call: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022
 Topic: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022-ST6AAM-C-01-01
 Type of action: HORIZON-JU-RIA
 Duration: 36 months

Figure 26 6G-SANDBOX Poster

Figure 27: 6G-SANDBOX Tri-Fold Brochure

2.7.3.4 CONTACT EMAIL

A project-specific contact email which is linked with the Contact Form on the website is already launched. Interested users and communities can use this form to communicate with the project coordinator’s team. This is a continuous-communication activity planned from M1 to M36 plus three years after project end.

2.7.3.5 NEWSLETTER

A quarterly Newsletter will be published to communicate the latest news of the project. Each issue of the newsletter will be announced to the public via 6G-SANDBOX communication channels, including the website and the social media platforms. This is a continuous-communication activity planned from M4 to M36.

Figure 28: 6G-SANDBOX Newsletter Template (first and last page)

2.7.3.6 PRESS RELEASES, ARTICLES, INTERVIEWS AND VIDEOS

These will be published at regular intervals and usually in parallel/following major dissemination events. This is a continuous-communication activity planned from M3 to M36.

2.7.3.7 TRADITIONAL MASS MEDIA

To increase the potential audience of 6G-SANDBOX, public media such as newspapers, online magazines and relevant third-party websites might also be used. These sources will be chosen based on findings during the project that point out which media optimally reaches the relevant target groups per use case. Those channels will be targeted specifically for the trial’s events. This activity is planned from M18 to M36.

The communication strategy is driven by **communication objectives** directly linked with the progress and maturity of the project realization (see Table 1) as well as the corresponding targeted audiences (see

Table 2). The exact strategy of communication will be refined during the project and will be guided by specific communication actions/measures drawing from the described communication approach. The following KPIs are set decidedly ambitious but realistic for the project communication in the table below (see Table 4).

Table 3: 6G-SANDBOX Communication KPIs

Table 4: 6G-SANDBOX Communication KPIs	
Channel	Activities/KPIs (M36)
Online presence (M1-M36)	6G-SANDBOX Website >5,000 website visitors ~2-minute Average duration of visits >5,000 Number of page views >100 website news
Social media (M1-M36)	6G-SANDBOX social media accounts in Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram: >1,000 Number of total followers in all social media channels >750 Number of total posts in all social media >50,000 Engagements/Reactions/Reach
Press releases, Articles and Interviews (M3-M36)	>10 Press releases >15 Online Articles and Interviews Communication of project news, events, results; Increased awareness.
Promotional material	Leaflets: >2 versions

(M4-M36)	Posters: >2 versions Stickers
Video clips (M7-M36)	>10 Number of videos
Newsletters (M3-M36)	12 Issues of eNewsletters (issued quarterly)

2.7.4 DISSEMINATION PLAN

The 6G-SANDBOX dissemination action plan is focused on the creation of high-quality level of activities, so the scientific knowledge and technological advances generated from the project can be transmitted to the research, academia, related industry, vertical communities, SMEs and end-users and ultimately have a clear impact on the society while supporting the European Innovation pathway. Dissemination activities deal mainly with making public to a wide scientific and technical audience and the targeted stakeholders, and as a next step to explain how the findings can be exploited.

6G-SANDBOX's dissemination activities will differ in intensity based on the time evolution of the project. To better monitor the intensity and set the corresponding goals per time period, the dissemination activities will be divided and carried out in the following three annual phases:

Phase 1: Year 1 (M1-M12)

Phase 2: Year 2 (M13-M24)

Phase 3: Year 3 (M25-M36) and after project ends

The intensity will differ per phase and the set goals should reflect this differentiation. As a result, **a split ratio percentage of approximately 20/30/50 will be used for setting the minimum planned goals per phase.** Potential deviations between phases will be acceptable given the progress and achievements of the project but the final targets shall be met.

The set metrics, targets, and goals for the 6G-SANDBOX publications and dissemination's activities plan are summarized below in Table 5.

Table 5: 6G-SANDBOX Dissemination KPIs per year

Planned Activities	Dissemination metrics	Overall Target	Period	Y1	Y2	Y3
# of scientific papers in journals and conferences	Number of publications	>60	M9-M36	4	20	36
# of presentations in scientific events, fairs, conferences and workshops	Number of presentations	>20	M3-M36	4	6	10
# of Poster sessions, Panel Discussions, webinars	Number of poster sessions, panel Discussion etc	>5	M13-M36	-	2	3
# of workshops/special sessions organised/co-organised	Number of events	>5	M18-M36	-	1	4
# of actions/liaison with other projects of the cluster and related associations	Number of actions	>10	M3-M36	2	3	5

# of events/conferences/fairs actively participated/attended	Number of events	>20	M3-M36	4	6	10
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Coordination, publication, and presentation of 6G-SANDBOX contributions to reputable international conferences, as well as peer reviewed journals and magazines, will be realized. Considering the focus of 6G-SANDBOX, the consortium will provide publications in the high-impact conferences and technical journals.

2.7.4.1 ORGANISATION OF DEDICATED 6G-SANDBOX WORKSHOPS AND WEBINARS

The 6G-SANDBOX Consortium will organise workshops and webinars primarily targeting the groups identified above. In this way, the introduction of 6G-SANDBOX results to other organisations will be accelerated and potential business end users will be properly informed on all aspects relating to 6G-SANDBOX. Independent experts both from industry and academia will also be invited. These workshops will aim to be offered in conjunction with other major events.

2.7.4.2 PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS, CONFERENCES AND PUBLIC INDUSTRY EXHIBITIONS

A high level of visibility will be achieved for the project by organising/participating in public exhibitions such as EUCNC, Mobile World Congress and industry/operator fairs (e.g., NGMN) contributing demonstrations of project achievements to approach business stakeholders.

2.7.4.3 ACADEMIC DISSEMINATION

6G-SANDBOX will disseminate its key findings and solutions to the academic community to be used by research and teaching programs.

2.5 MONITORING, CONTROL AND EVALUATION OF COMMUNICATION/ DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The effectiveness of 6G-SANDBOX communication channels will be constantly monitored throughout the project's lifespan, and corrective actions will be taken as needed. The objectives and targets of the 6G-SANDBOX communication plan must be met without deviations or underperformance. As a result, a set of tools is used to ensure the effective and ongoing monitoring and evaluation of communication channels and activities.

2.5.1 MONITOR AND CONTROL PROCESSES

The 6G-SANDBOX partners will use the Microsoft SharePoint platform, as the online repository tool for sharing material and content. For clear cooperation and better distribution of the material among partners, this digital environment is divided into sections – folders and sub-folders. The SharePoint platform plays an important role in the successful collaboration and alignment of the Consortium's members. This specific online repository file is segregated in dedicated folders created per Work Package and Task (see Figure 29:). Also, there are folders created for the deliverables and for project coordination facilities (e.g., templates and other materials for public use). Furthermore, there is an option for online editing of files, a feature which is particularly useful in documenting and editing communication activities or files in general.

Figure 29: Microsoft SharePoint Repository

A process based on the use of two separate Excel files in SharePoint was established for the efficient recording of each partner's dissemination activities. These two files, which serve two distinct functions, can be found in the WP6 Folder => T6.2 Dissemination and Communication. The first file is titled "WP6 Activities reporting" and is completed after a partner finishes a project-related communication/dissemination activity. The second, titled "Posts for Social Media," invites partners to suggest potential content for upcoming posts on the project's communication channels and/or news for the News webpage.

There is a specific procedure concerning these Excel files. Each partner should update these files with the information that they want to be communicated by INFOLYSIS partner. Every Excel file has specific details that must be submitted by the interested partner. The "WP6 Activities reporting" Excel file details are: *Item - Authors/Partners - Activity Title - Target (Event, Location, Date) – Description*. Also, there are two extra columns to control whether this content has been posted or has been included in the Newsletter.

# Item	Authors/Partners	Activity Title	Target (Event, Location, Date)	Detailed Description	Posted	Newsletter Issue
1	Keysight	Press Release	Online	Online Press Release was released on the 5th of January to inform about the Project	YES	1
2	Consortium	Kick Off Meeting	Leuven, Belgium, 11-12/01		YES	
3	Lenovo	Presentation	ETSI Research Conference, 6-8 February	<p>"In this presentation, Dr. Salkintzis provided a high-level overview of the 6G-SANDBOX project and explained how it can help us in our journey to 6G. The main objective of this project is build an experimentation platform that can help us evaluate new technologies towards 6G and measure important 6G KPIs and KVs. It was also pointed out that the 6G-SANDBOX project is open to third-parties willing to contribute either with new technologies, or with new use-cases and experiments. The most important question from the audience was whether the 6G-SANDBOX platform will be able to interoperate with other experimentation platforms towards creating federated experimentation platforms."</p> <p>On the 15th of February, our Technical Coordinator, Dr. Pedro Merino, from University of Malaga, presented the 6G-6G-SANDBOX project in the context of the #SNS Luncheon webinars, which were organised by SNS JU. The first webinar, presented Stream /Strand B5 & C & D projects addressing 6G holistic systems, SNS experimental infrastructures & SNS Large scale</p>	YES	

Figure 30: WP6 Activities Reporting File

Additionally, on the “Posts for Social Media” Excel file, the requested details are Item # - Partners - Activity Type -Text For Posting - Social Media Channel.

Item #	Partners	Activity Type	Text For Posting	Social Media Channel
1	Keysight	Press Release	<p>Keysight, 6G-SANDBOX Project Coordinator, along with the rest 16 project partners, announced today through a press release the details of the 6G-SANDBOX project (an Horizon Europe SNS Stream C research and innovation project) aiming at developing a pan-European testbed for 6G experimentation and validation of 5G-advanced and 6G capabilities.</p> <p>You can read more here: https://lnkd.in/d/da6dftXq</p>	All

Figure 31: WP6 – Excel File to cover Posts for Social Media

The information provided in these Excel files is extremely helpful as it gives an idea about the event and the activity performed by a partner. Additionally, it helps to communicate it better and to choose the most efficient communication channel for each activity and prepare equivalent material if there is not any.

Furthermore, each partner should upload any related material such as presentations, webinars, papers, etc. from the event in which they participated, in WP6 corresponding folder entitled *Partners’ WP6 Events Dissemination Material* (see Figure 32:). Every partner must create a new subfolder for each new event.

Finally, at the WP6 folder, the Dissemination and Communication Procedure document is available for the Partners, as a reminder.

Figure 32: WP6 – Events Dissemination Material Document

2.7.5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND STATISTICAL DASHBOARDS

Through the Google Data Studio, the monthly data of the communication channels are processed and analysed. The produced statistical data are internally released in graphical Dashboards (accessible online at SharePoint through static Google Data Studio URLs).

Specifically, the 6G-SANDBOX Social Media Google Data Studio Statistical dashboards will be regularly issued at quarterly intervals. Moreover, custom timeframe periods can be statistically analysed and visualized in dashboards (e.g., 6 months, annually, etc.). Every communication channel will be reported on its own dedicated statistical dashboard, which will include a variety of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), aiming always to assist on achieving efficient performance assessment. The comparison of dashboards referring to different periods will reveal positive changes, trends, or deviations, which will derive from the evolution of communication strategy and the project progress (e.g., followers increase, number of posts, impact achievement, penetration increase and visibility awareness, etc.).

If the statistics of the dashboards show a performance decline in numbers (leading to reduced impact) for a specific communication channel, this observation will trigger to proactively revise and improve the communication strategy of the specific communication channel.

In summary, Google Data Studio is the main data tool that will provide feedback, control, monitoring, and statistical analysis concerning the efficiency and effectiveness of 6G-SANDBOX communication channels' impact at our audience and stakeholders.

For indicative purposes, preliminary graphic dashboards referring to the statistical analysis of the January 2023 social communication channels activity is presented in the following paragraphs.

Figure 33: WP6 – Google Analytics Platform

Google Analytics will be used by the communication team not only for monitoring and evaluating the website’s efficiency, but the collected data will be also fed to Google Data Studio (<https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/6968b8dd-5261-45a9-8243-dae2ca35c673/page/pmtsB>) for summarizing the Google Analytics reports into a more comprehensive visual statistical overview of the website performance on a quarterly basis.

Figure 34: depicts an example of a such report.

Figure 34: WP6 – Google Data Studio Platform

2.7.6 6G-SANDBOX FACEBOOK STATISTICAL DASHBOARD

The 6G-SANDBOX Facebook Dashboard (<https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/8ba0ff2-51ee-447a-ad8a-4c606069fe7b/page/j5mpB>) will provide progress diagrams related to page views and page engagement throughout the examined period. Period and Total Statistics will also be included with various KPIs and metrics. Period Statistics refer to the statistics (such as number of posts) during a specified period, while Total Statistics provide similar information about the whole duration of the project.

Figure 35: WP6 – Facebook Statistics Dashboard

2.7.7 6G-SANDBOX TWITTER STATISTICAL DASHBOARD

The 6G-SANDBOX Twitter Dashboard (<https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/6a65ed0d-da58-4bcb-9389-ddf116daa7da/page/4YFqB>) includes a diagram with likes per tweets and a table with tweet's likes, impressions and engagement. Period and Total Statistics include retweets, likes, impressions engagement rate and followers among other important values and metrics.

Figure 36: WP6 –Twitter Statistics Dashboard

2.7.8 6G-SANDBOX LINKEDIN STATISTICAL DASHBOARD

The 6G-SANDBOX LinkedIn Dashboard (<https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/594e2db8-2413-4a95-a500-7212d506c796/page/1SSqB>) focuses on likes and views on post level (per post), and their evolution through the examined time period. Period and Total Statistics will also be included following the same format as mentioned in the Twitter section above.

Figure 37: WP6 –LinkedIn Statistics Dashboard

2.7.9 6G-SANDBOX INSTAGRAM STATISTICAL DASHBOARD

The 6G-SANDBOX Instagram Dashboard (<https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/2ed8de5e-39fc-467b-83f2-835afacc631c/page/rKQqB>) shares the same concept as the previous ones. The statistics will be provided on a post level, and will show the progress on post impression, reach and likes. The total number of posts, likes, followers, follows, etc. will be included in the Period and Total Statistics section.

Figure 38: WP6 – Instagram Statistics Dashboard

3 STANDARDIZATION AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The Standardization and Exploitation Strategy for the 6G-SANDBOX aims to ensure that the project's research outcomes are effectively disseminated, adopted, and commercialized in the market. The strategy outlines a set of activities and approaches that are designed to promote standardization, exploitation, and commercialization of the 6G-SANDBOX research outcomes. The strategy is composed of the following five phases.

1. Standardization

The first phase of the strategy is to establish standardization initiatives that promote the adoption of the 6G-SANDBOX research outcomes. This includes identifying the key stakeholders in the industry and establishing partnerships and collaborations with them. The project will engage with relevant standardization bodies, such as the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), to ensure that (a) the 6G-SANDBOX facility is implemented in alignment with the industry standards and (b) that the research outcomes are contributed to the relevant standards. Lenovo and several other partners are already actively participating in several standardization bodies and will exploit their participation expertise for realizing the standardization strategy.

2. Exploitation

The second phase of the strategy is to ensure that the research outcomes are effectively exploited. This involves formalising and prioritizing the project's outcomes from the business viewpoint, identifying the commercialization opportunities for the resulting list and developing a roadmap for their commercialization. The project will establish a network of partners, including start-ups, SMEs, and large enterprises, to facilitate the exploitation of the research outcomes. As a common practice in all R&D EU funded projects, various types of partners participate, including universities, research centres, commercial companies and SMEs, and depending on their expertise and areas of interest, the exploitation strategy and activities vary accordingly. Universities and Research Centres focus on exploitation activities regarding research items, while commercial companies and SMEs are mainly involved with the exploitation of commercially oriented products. In the light of this diversity, we can identify the following five major categories of exploitable outcomes to focus:

- **Product development**, which includes the introduction of new products/features (together with a roadmap definition) and the product validation that increases the technology readiness level (TRL) towards a successful deployment. This outcome category is related mostly to commercial companies and SMEs.
- **Business development**, which includes enhancement of existing processes/services and/or the creation of new services/activities. This outcome category is also related mostly to commercial companies and SMEs.
- **Research achievements**, including publications, IPRs and prototypes and can be produced by all partners.
- **Standardization** is a process tool through which the commercialization and sustainability of a project's results can be supported. Partners that are actively involved in standardization and regulatory activities may promote the results of the project to provide technical contributions to relevant standards bodies.
- **Start-Up companies**. These are established mainly by Universities and Research Centres in order to use one or more of the project's exploitable outcomes and as such indirectly pursue a Product development outcome.

Furthermore, the contributions from partners are of varying focus and type, and the results can be identified as follows:

- **Demonstrators** – Demonstrations of one or more 5G!Drones results/products in the field or in lab environment; either as Proof of Concept (PoC) or as Solutions addressing specific end-user needs. Demonstrators are usually joint results of more than one partner and partner type.
- **Prototypes** – Stand-alone, modular products which have been either developed or enhanced in the context of the project. Prototypes may be developed by commercial companies and SMEs or by academic or research initiatives with no direct commercialization capability.
- **Validation Activities** – Activities aiming at validating the functionalities of specific products; these can be considered as exploitation activities aiming at increasing the technology readiness level of the associated products.
- **Contributions to standardization and publications** – Indirectly exploitable results delivered to the industry through standardization and dissemination paths.
- **Other Achievements** – Activities/tools aiming at enhancing processes/services related to the introduction/deployment of the project results (e.g., studies, algorithms, techno-economical tools, knowledge transfer, etc.).

Under these assumptions, an initial perception for the categorization of the project outcomes is already formulated and is graphically depicted as shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39: 6G-SANDBOX Considered Project Outcome Classification

3. Commercialization

The third phase of the strategy is to commercialize the research outcomes. This involves establishing a business model for the commercialization of the research outcomes and identifying potential customers and end-users. The project will develop a marketing and sales strategy that targets potential customers and end-users and will work closely with its partners to ensure that the research outcomes are effectively marketed and sold. As part

of the commercialization, various business development methodologies shall be evaluated to be applied such as the value proposition canvas (VPC)² or the business canvas model³ methods.

4. Intellectual Property

The fourth phase of the strategy is to protect the project's intellectual property. This involves identifying the intellectual property generated by the project and developing a strategy for its protection. The project will work to ensure that the project's intellectual property is effectively protected and that the project's partners are aware of their rights and responsibilities.

5. Monitoring and Evaluation

The final phase of the strategy is to monitor and evaluate the project's progress. This involves establishing metrics for measuring the impact of the project's research outcomes and tracking their adoption and commercialization. The project will establish a monitoring and evaluation framework that tracks the progress of the project's research outcomes and provides feedback to the project team on their performance.

By following the above Standardization and Exploitation Strategy, the 6G-SANDBOX research project will ensure that its research outcomes are effectively disseminated, adopted, and commercialized in the market. This will contribute to the project's overall success and impact in the industry.

3.2 PRELIMINARY PLAN OF STANDARDIZATION ACTIVITIES

The 6G-SANDBOX project aims to develop and test new technologies and KPIs/KVIs for the upcoming 6G mobile networks. As part of this project, the standardization activities will be essential to ensure that the technologies developed for the 6G-SANDBOX facility can be deployed and used reliably and securely across different testbed networks and devices.

The preliminary plan of standardization activities for the 6G-SANDBOX project includes the following:

- Identify key stakeholders: The first step is to identify the key stakeholders who will be involved in the standardization activities. The following is a preliminary list of stakeholders/project partners:

Stakeholder	Involvement in standardization bodies
Lenovo	ETSI, 3GPP, O-RAN
UMA	ETSI, 3GPP
ISRD	O-RAN

Define the scope: The next step is to define the scope of the standardization activities. This includes identifying the key technologies that will be developed as part of the 6G-SANDBOX project and determining which standards will need to be developed or updated to support these technologies. The following is a preliminary list of standardization bodies/working groups in the scope of the project.

² "Value Proposition Canvas" [Online], <https://www.b2binternational.com/research/methods/fag/what-is-the-value-proposition-canvas>, Accessed Dec 2019

³ "Business Model Canvas" [Online], <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>, Accessed: Dec 2019. HORIZON 2020 – WORK PROGRAMME 2014-2015, Technology readiness levels (TRL), https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

SDO / WG	Relevance with the project
3GPP SA2	<p>General architecture of facility</p> <p>Multiaccess communication</p> <p>Network Exposure capabilities</p> <p>Network Slicing (for supporting Trial Networks)</p>
3GPP SA6	Application Exposure capabilities
3GPP SA5	Network Management and Orchestration
ETSI RIS	<p>Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) can be used to enhance the performance of wireless communication systems, increase network capacity, and reduce interference. It is planned to integrate RIS into one or more of the 6G-SANDBOX testbeds.</p>
ETSI INT	<p>The ETSI Core Network and Interoperability Testing (INT) group produces test purposes, test descriptions, and TTCN-3 test cases to enable interoperability testing of the core network elements and covering the single-network, interconnect and roaming scenarios. Therefore, the ETSI INT is deemed as highly relevant with the 6G-SANDBOX's scope.</p>
ETSI NFV	<p>The ETSI NFV (Network Functions Virtualization) produces a set of standards that enable the virtualization of network functions such as firewalls, load balancers, and other components, such as 5G/6G network functions.</p> <p>While there is no direct connection between ETSI NFV and the 6G-SANDBOX project, NFV is expected to play an important role in the development and deployment of 6G networks. The virtualization of network functions enables greater flexibility and agility in deploying and managing network services, which is crucial in the fast-evolving and complex 6G ecosystem.</p> <p>Therefore, while the 6G-SANDBOX project may not directly rely on ETSI NFV, the use of NFV is likely to be an important consideration in the development of the 6G-SANDBOX facility.</p>
O-RAN	<p>O-RAN is a global alliance of mobile network operators, vendors, and research institutions that aims to create a more open and intelligent RAN architecture. The goal of O-RAN is to promote interoperability between different vendors' equipment and software, reduce the cost of RAN deployment and operation, and accelerate innovation in the mobile industry.</p> <p>The 6G-SANDBOX plans to evolve the underlying testbeds into O-RAN compatible testbeds, capable of running xApps and/or rApps for improved performance and resource utilization. Therefore, O-RAN specifications are deemed highly relevant with the 6G-SANDBOX project.</p>
ITU-T	<p>ITU-T recommendation Q. 4068 presents is highly relevant with 6G-SANDBOX since it defines a set of open APIs for interoperable testbed federations, able to manage not only the interconnection and the interoperability of testbeds in a federation, but also to handle resources advertisement, allocation and provision.</p>

Develop a roadmap: Once the scope has been defined, a roadmap should be developed outlining the key standardization activities that will need to be undertaken over the course of the project. This should include a timeline for each activity, as well as the resources required to complete it.

- Engage with standards bodies: The project team should engage with relevant standards bodies, such as the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), to ensure that the standardization activities align with existing standards and to contribute to the development of new standards where necessary.
- Conduct trials and testing: As the project progresses, trials and testing should be conducted to ensure that the technologies developed meet the required standards and can be deployed in a reliable and secure manner.
- Monitor and update: The standardization activities should be monitored throughout the project to ensure that they remain on track and that any necessary updates or changes are made in a timely manner.
- Disseminate information: Finally, the results of the standardization activities should be disseminated to relevant stakeholders to ensure that they are aware of the latest developments and standardization activities and impact of the project. This can include publishing papers, presenting at conferences, and engaging with industry associations, such as 6G-IA, etc.

3.3 PRELIMINARY PLAN OF EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

The perceived plan for implementing the exploitation strategy assume the following steps:

1. The project members compose an exhaustive list of foreseen project outcomes, that are classified accordingly i.e., as depicted in Figure 39
2. The list is prioritized, considering target customer segments and market demands, to agree on the set of high potential outcomes. The main focus on the selection is around project-wide exploitable results beyond the individual exploitation plans of each partner.
3. For each exploitable/business outcome, a detailed business analysis is performed that can include technology Readiness (TRL)⁴ identification, Gap Analysis (SWOT)⁵ and business modelling.

For the list of exploitable outcomes with promising results, a more in-depth analysis (e.g., Business Value Proposition or Lean Canvas) can be filled, to pave the way towards the formulation of a Business Case.

In parallel with the execution of the exploitation strategy plan, the following actions will be considered to confirm and/or calibrate the approach and final results:

- Technology Demonstrations: The project team will showcase the technology developed during the project through public demonstrations and exhibitions. This will help attract potential partners and investors, while also creating awareness about the benefits of 6G technology and of the 6G-SANDBOX experimentation facility.
- Patents and Licensing: The project team will identify potential patents that could be filed for the technology developed during the project and could license it to interested parties. This could create a

⁴Technology Readiness Level [Online]

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

⁵ SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats analysis)

market for the 6G-SANDBOX experimentation facility. At the early stages of the project, it is yet unclear whether any patent filing opportunities will emerge; however, such opportunities will be monitored and identified as part of the project's exploitation activities.

- **Industry Partnerships:** The project team will identify opportunities to collaborate with industry partners to develop and possibly commercialize 6G-SANDBOX technology. This can help bridge the gap between research and commercialization and provide real-world testing environments for the 6G technology.
- The project team can offer training and education programs to students and industry professionals interested in 6G technology. This will help create a skilled workforce for this technology and foster innovation in the field.
- **Policy Recommendations:** The project team can make policy recommendations to governments and regulatory bodies regarding the development and deployment of 6G technology. This will help create a supportive regulatory environment for the technology and ensure its successful adoption.
- **Standardization:** The project team can contribute to the development of global standards for 6G technology. This will help ensure interoperability and compatibility between different networks and devices, while also creating a level playing field for different stakeholders in the industry.

By following the above preliminary plan of exploitation activities, the 6G-SANDBOX project can maximize the impact of its research and development efforts, while also creating a sustainable business model for the technology.

3.4 ADVISORY BOARD TO FACILITATE IMPACT AND PROVIDE EXTERNAL PERSPECTIVES

6G-SANDBOX establishes an advisory board composed of expert members bringing a technology perspective, as well as a vertical user perspective. - The advisory board will be consulted to guide the consortium for critical decisions such as the content of the open calls, the communication approach to motivate the researcher to increase the use of the testbed, the decision to add activities within the project etc...

The following individuals are members of the advisory board

Vertical user perspective

1. Prof. Carlos E. Palau Salvador, Universitat Politècnica de València,
2. Tian hong Loh, NPL UK

Technology perspective

3. Valerio Frascolla, Intel
4. Rui L. Aguiar, University of AveiroSébastien Faye, LIST Luxembourg
5. Paul Muschamp, British Telecom

4 COLLABORATION AT SNS PROGRAM LEVEL AND OTHER PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

4.1 SNS JU AND 6G IA BODIES AND WORK GROUPS

6G-SANDBOX is aware of the requirement to implement this project as part of a programme of complementary grants as specified in the SNS work programme. In particular, it acknowledges the roles and commitments of the EC, the SNS JU board, the Network Europe technology platform, the 6G Infrastructure Association, the 5G for Europe Action Plan and commits to constructive interactions with these bodies. 6G-SANDBOX commits to work with its peer SNS JU projects as required under article 7 of the grant agreement that requires arrangements set out in a written collaboration agreement with the participants of the other project.

This implies an organizational structure for the SNS JU, although the details of it are a work-in-progress. However, we assume that the governance of the programme will be very similar to the governance of its predecessor programme 5G PPP. Hence, we assume a Steering Board (SB), a Technology Board (TB) and several Working Groups (WGs) as the working structure of the SNS JU projects’ collaboration mechanisms. The 6G-SANDBOX has implemented the following measures:

- Appointment of an SB mandated representative (project coordinator), who will represent the project in the SB meetings and will participate and contribute to the SNS JU activities and report progress against programme commitments. A deputy SB member has been appointed as well
- Appointment of a TB mandated representative (technical manager), who will represent the project at TB meetings and will contribute fully to actions to determine the progress against the programme key performance and key value indicators. A deputy TB member has been appointed as well.
- Appointment of representatives (and their deputies) to join WGs, who will contribute to and, as necessary, edit position papers, deliverables, and reports from the working groups, proactively driving working groups closely related to the project goals.

It is fully understood by 6G-SANDBOX that, while the grant agreements are contracts at project level, success may be evaluated in the programme context. So, under article 7 of the complementary grant agreements, this programme level responsibility is understood as part of the project undertaking. 6G-SANDBOX has allocated sufficient resources for the interaction with the SNS JU programme at all levels, e.g., SB, TB, WGs, as well as joint dissemination activities and programme representation. Sufficient budget has been planned for travel costs and contributions to programme level events and dissemination material. Resources for participation in SB and TB are included in Task 6.4; for participation at WGs at the work packages that relate to the subject of the working groups. The bodies and work groups are differentiated in SNS JU project bodies and WGs, and 6G IA workgroups as follows:

SNS JU projects bodies and work groups	6G IA work groups
Steering board	Open Smart Networks and Services
Technology board	Pre-Standardization
5G/Beyond 5G Architecture	Spectrum
Software Networks	Vision and Societal Challenges
Network Management & QoS (dormant)	Security

Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation	Trials
	5G for CAM
	SME (Networld Europe)

The project has appointed the following individuals as contacts to the activities of the SNS JU programme:

Body/group	Liaison person	Deputy liaison person
Steering board (PM)	Michael Dieudonne (Keysight)	Pedro Merino (Univ. Of Malaga)
Technology board (TM)	Pedro Merino (Univ. Of Malaga)	Dimitris Tsolkas (Fogus Innovations & Services)
5G/Beyond 5G Architecture	Harilaos Koumaras (NCSR)	Anastasius Gavras (Eurescom) Dimitris Tsolkas (Fogus Innovations & Services)
Software Networks	Adam Flizikowski (ISR)	
Network Management & QoS (dormant)		
Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation	Anastasius Gavras (Eurescom)	Michael Dieudonne (Keysight)
Open Smart Networks and Services	George Makropoulos (NCSR)	Nikolaos Gkatzios (INFOLYSIS) Dimitris Tsolkas (Fogus Innovations & Services)
Pre-Standardization		
Spectrum (not active)		
Vision and Societal Challenges	Anastasius Gavras (Eurescom)	Ioanna Mesogiti (COSM)
Security	Nikolaos Gkatzios (INFOLYSIS)	
Trials	Pedro Merino (Univ. Of Malaga)	
5G for CAM	Dimitris Fragkos (NCSR)	
SME	Vaios Koumaras (INFOLYSIS)	Dimitris Tsolkas (Fogus Innovations & Services)
Communications (not listed under https://6g-ia.eu)	Anastasius Gavras (Eurescom)	Marina Koulaloglou (INFOLYSIS)

4.1.1 ASSESSMENT OF WORKLOAD FOR THE INTERACTION WITH WORK GROUPS

In the following section, we assess the principal workload for the liaison persons listed above in their engagement with the SNS JU programme Work Groups (WGs). The information below is valid for all WGs and differs in case can a project member is assuming a chair or co-chair function of a WG.

The main workload for the liaison person is to participate in the conference calls and meetings of the WGs. Physical meetings are not common for the work of the WGs but can only occur under exceptional circumstances. Conference calls are the norm, and depending on the WG plan, take place every two to four weeks and last normally no more than 90 minutes (with the exception perhaps of the architecture WG in 5G PPP that required 120 minutes). This primary activity can be shared also with the deputy liaison person.

Depending on the topics being discussed, it is the responsibility of the liaison person to report back to the project or introduce project proposals to the WG. Examples of these activities are:

- If the WG drafts a white paper to which the project can contribute, ask the related project partners to compile contributions to the white paper in production. Usually, these contributions range from a few paragraphs up to a few pages. The contributions are typically communicated via the liaison person between the project and the WG.
- If the project wants to draft a white paper and it seems like a good idea to engage with other projects, then bring the project's proposal for a joint white paper into the WG for discussion/decision. In this case normally the WG will ask the proposing project to ensure that an editor is available. Editorship of a white paper is obviously more work, but editorship is not necessarily assigned to the liaison person by default.
- Often the WGs organise project presentations along the interest topics of the WG. These presentations can be used to directly liaise with projects in case of substantial mutual interest. The liaison person mediates for a good presentation to the WG or presents project contributions directly.
- WGs organise webinars or conference sessions to which the projects interested on the subject contribute to the organisation and execution. Similarly, this activity is not necessarily assigned to the liaison person by default.
- Occasionally review draft white papers for quality.

The general interaction pattern can be intermittent during white paper drafting.

The workload for chair or co-chair is higher due the following additional duties to:

- Organise conference calls and meetings
- Provide agenda and minutes of conference calls and meeting
- Track activities of the WG for reporting to the steering board
- Maintain the terms of reference document for the WG
- Report regularly to the steering board

4.2 DIRECT COLLABORATION WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

6G-SANDBOX collaborates or plans to collaborate with other collaborative projects in Europe and potentially worldwide. Beyond SNS JU projects, several projects of the 5G PPP are still active and with which a collaboration is meaningful. Finally, 6G-SANDBOX is preparing an MoU that can facilitate collaboration with the European Space Agency (ESA). The following table lists the projects, the area of collaboration and the main partner(s) through which the collaboration is being facilitated.

Table 6: Collaboration with other projects and initiatives

Project / Initiative	Liaison partner	Collaboration topics
Hexa-X (5G PPP)		
ARIADNE (5G PPP)	EURE	Channel models
6G-BRAINS (5G PPP)	EURE	Channel models
EVOLVED-5G	UMA, NCSR, TID, FOG, INF, COS	CAPIF, NEF, Network Apps, Malaga and Athens platforms
6G-BRICKS	ISRD	Cell free Virtual RAN
CampusOS	FOKUS	6G-Sandbox attempts to establish a collaboration with the German Lighthouse project CampusOS as such that CampusOS may use the toolset available at the Berlin Platform of 6G-Sandbox to conduct performance evaluations of 5G campus networks.
ESA	TID, UMA, KEYS, ON	<p>Connect 6G-SANDBOX Málaga Testbed to ESA 6G Lab at Oxford (UK);</p> <p>Connect other 6G-SANDBOX sites to ESA labs when they install NTN support;</p> <p>Conduct trials and demos integrating satellite and terrestrial 5G and 6G technologies and implementing use cases in different vertical domains;</p> <p>Set up of an open innovation laboratory to be potentially interconnected with other open innovation laboratories in ESA facilities or in other locations;</p>

5 INITIAL PLAN FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF OPEN CALLS

In order to enable implementation of 6G use cases by using the 6G-SANDBOX experimental infrastructure, the project provides 20% of its budget for participation of third parties through the competitive open calls, which will be organized during the project lifetime. To ensure a fully open and transparent process of selecting the third parties, a corresponding process will be implemented by considering all relevant aspects of implementation of competitive open/public calls, such as:

- Proper definition of technical scope of the open calls
- Expectations on the successful proposers,
- Clear formal conditions for participation in the call,
- Provision of all needed open call documentation,
- A secured online proposal submission tool,
- Fast support for the proposers - helpdesk - as needed,
- Wide promotion of the open calls, an
- Evaluation of proposals received by independent experts.

5.1 GENERAL OPEN CALLS PLANNING

The 6G-SANDBOX is planning to organize the project open calls through the following three phases:

- 1st Open Call for new infrastructures and functionalities
- 2nd Open Call for experiments and missing functionalities
- 3rd Open Call for experiments.

Thus, the intention of the 1st OC is to enlarge and make the 6G-SANDBOX experimental infrastructure ready for advanced experimentation in the 3rd OC, but so far feasible for particular implementations during the 2nd OC. The 2nd OC might be also used for additional experimental and testing features of the 6G-SANDBOX, if the corresponding gaps will be identified by the consortium but will focus on initial experiments. The 3rd OC will be dedicated to experiments, running on the top of the advanced 6G-SANDBOX facilities.

Figure 39 6G-SANDBOX Open Calls timing presents the current planning for implementation of the 6G-SANDBOX open calls. For each of the calls, the needed time for OC definition including publication, evaluation and contracting, and the actual implementation are included in the timeline.

Figure 39 6G-SANDBOX Open Calls timing

Please, note that the open calls 2 and 3 might be implemented in several phases.

5.2 THE 1ST 6G-SANDBOX OPEN CALL

The definition of the 1st Open Call topics has been launched on the project start. For the time being, the following topics have been identified:

- AI Extensions of the 6G-SANDBOX NEF emulator
- Integrating LoRaWAN in the 6G-SANDBOX connectivity infrastructure
- Adding NWDAF Capabilities
- Adding NEF Capabilities
- Inclusion of Release 16 Devices
- Location information capability
- Integrated Sensing & Communication (ISAC) to save energy
- Full O-RAN solution
- OpenAirInterface / srsRAN SDR based (O)RAN solution
- Advanced channel models
- Flexible core distribution with NTN LEO (starlink) connection
- RAN extensions towards 6G RAN with new xApps
- Validation of Digital twin performance in realistic deployments
- ... further topics of community interest can be submitted as well!

We planned to complete the topic definition by April 2023, so that the first open call announcement can be widely distributed before opening the formal submission period, which will start late on 2 May 2023. The submission deadline will be on 3 July 2023 (17:00 CET).

For the 1st Open Call, the 6G-SANDBOX plans to offer around one-third of its budget allocated to cascade funding.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this document, the 6G-SANDBOX project Consortium laid down its first elaboration of the dissemination and exploitation plan. It includes further details on the identified targeted groups, for the dissemination and exploitation activities, as well as the first set of planned interactions with the groups. Furthermore, the initial planning for publications in journals and conferences have been updated as well as initial planning for participation at other events, organization of the project workshops, etc. Also, the initial plans for standardization and overall exploitation activities have been provided as well. Furthermore, the 6G-SANDBOX project indicated its commitment and planned involvement on the SNS program level.

The document also provides information on the completed project branding, which includes a clear definition of the project logo as well as other components of the graphical project identity. 6G-SANDBOX launched its website and further social media channels, such as LinkedIn, Twitter, etc.

Finally, the deliverable presents an initial plan for implementation of the 6G-SANDBOX open calls, which will be organized in three phases. For the time being, topics planned for the 1st OC are in discussion, as presented earlier in this report.

Finally, this deliverable should be considered as a living document, reporting on the updated plan and established 6G-SANDBOX dissemination environment, and will be continuously updated and reviewed during the project lifetime.

ANNEX 1

LOGO VARIATIONS

